

CERTAINTY Imperial College London's DMP

Version 0

Description

The Data Management Plan (DMP) for processed satellite data is created at Imperial College London to support the effective management and preservation of data generated during the CERTAINTY project.

The DMP for the processed data is designed to maximize the value, accessibility, and impact of the data produced, supporting the Grantham Institute's mission to produce research, training and innovation towards effective UK and international action on climate change and the environment

Funder

European Commission||EC

Grant

CERTAINTY

Researchers

Edward Gryspeerdt (orcid:0000-0002-3815-4756)

Organizations

The Grantham Institute for Climate Change Imperial College
London

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [CERTAINTY Imperial College London's DMP](#)

Description:

The Data Management Plan (DMP) for processed satellite data is created at Imperial College London to support the effect management and preservation of data generated during the CERTAINTY project.

The DMP for the processed data is designed to maximize the value, accessibility, and impact of the data produced, supporting the Grantham Institute's mission to produce research, training and innovation towards effective UK and international action on climate change and the environment

Researchers:

[Edward Gryspeerdt \(orcid:0000-0002-3815-4756\)](#)

Organizations:

[The Grantham Institute for Climate Change](#) [Imperial College London](#)

Contact: [Anca Hienola](#)

2. Funding

Funding organizations: [European Commission](#)||[EC](#)

Grants: [CERTAINTY](#)

Project: [CERTAINTY](#)

3. License

License: [CC-BY-4.0](#)

Access Rights: [Public](#)

4. Templates

Descriptions

Processed satellite data

Processed satellite data e.g. estimates of radiative forcing and constraints on aerosol-cloud interactions.

This product will be designed for comparison with global climate models and provide an uncertainty range based on existing estimates of these effects, determined through a comparison of existing methods.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

This data will be produced during the project from the linked datasets.

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Derived or compiled

Processed satellite data for constraining aerosol-cloud interactions. This data is derived from the linked data sources and designed to be used to constrain

atmospheric and aerosol-climate models.

1.1.5 What is its format?

netcdf

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

1000000000

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information
- To make informed decisions
- To combine with other data

Data will be used to study processes, evaluate model output and constrain aerosol-cloud interactions. Existing data (such as climatologies of cloud properties) provide poor constraints on the aerosol and cloud processes necessary for this. This datasets will be created from the linked observational and reanalysis datasets

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Processed/derived from other satellite datasets, e.g. MODIS, GOES, SEVIRI, EarthCare

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers
- Education

Project partners, for evaluating model output in other work packages and tasks.

Other researchers, as new constraints on the strength of aerosol-cloud interactions and the aerosol effective radiative forcing. This will build on the work of the related model-analysis work packages.

Estimates of the aerosol effective radiative forcing are also useful for researchers working in other fields, due to a strong role in the calculation of the remaining carbon budget.

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

CF (Climate and Forecast) Metadata Conventions

The datafiles created will be CF-compliant, a common standard for climate science.

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

Descriptive

We offer descriptive metadata that enriches data or information resources with detailed information about their content, context, and structure, thereby improving their findability and practical use.

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

- Registry/Catalogue
- Metadata repository

The metadata will be searchable through the CEDA repository, where the output will be submitted.

<https://catalogue.ceda.ac.uk/>

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

The CEDA catalogue supports the use of keywords

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

No

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

The CEDA Archive

<https://catalogue.ceda.ac.uk/>

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

- Follows repository standards
- Details terms of use
- Has an open access content policy
- Supports retention

3.2.1.4 Add appropriate arrangements made with the repository(ies) where the described dataset will be deposited

Small data products (such as those created here) in natural environment related sciences are archived at CEDA free of charge.

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.6 Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?

CEDA provides DOIs

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

processed satellite data

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

Open, although a certain embargo period might be applied

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

Throughout the project's duration, the dataset might be subject to an embargo of up to two years. During this period, access to the data will be restricted, but project partners can obtain access. Once the embargo period concludes and the project is completed, the dataset will become publicly available, and accessible to all under the CC BY 4.0 license.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

Yes. However, we will not have closed datasets

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

Direct links are provided

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

Yes

CF (Climate and Forecast) Metadata Conventions

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

Yes

The dataset will be linked with the related scientific articles and also with the input data.

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

- Readme files
- Codebooks
- Data cleaning
- Analyses
- Variable definitions
- Units of measurement
- Negative results sharing

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

The CEDA archive support the use of data beyond the lifetime of the project. This will be supported with documentation and examples of use provided in related publications. Should the analysis be appropriate, it will be added to community tools, such as Obs4MIP or ESMValTool

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

Input data provenance will be linked in the metadata.

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

Data conform to format specification

CF compliance will be checked with standard tools

<https://cfchecker.ncas.ac.uk/>

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

Storage

Small data products (such as those created here) in natural environment related sciences are archived at CEDA free of charge.

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

- Use of national infrastructure
- Use of institution infrastructure

Small data products (such as those created here) in natural environment related sciences are archived at CEDA free of charge.

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Edward Gryspeerdt (orcid:0000-0002-3815-4756)

Research lead

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

Passwords

5.1.2 What conditions do the security measures meet?

- Data access
- Data storage
- Data transmission
- Data recovery
- Data sharing

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

Yes

7.1.2 Documentation of other procedures

All the minimum conditions listed in Science Europe Guidance Document are covered by the WP6 Open Science and Data management

ERA5 meteorological data

The analysis data from ERA-5 that includes the vertical profile of temperature, wind and humidity

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

Re-used

ERA5 data will be utilized to initialize the model.

For licence, citation and DOI go to

<https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/reanalysis-era5-single-levels?tab=overview>

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Derived or compiled

ERA5 is the fifth generation ECMWF reanalysis for the global climate and weather for the past 8 decades.

Reanalysis combines model data with observations from across the world into a globally complete and consistent dataset.

1.1.5 What is its format?

GRIB, NetCDF

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

10000000000000

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To develop a product

These data provide a best-estimate of the state of the atmosphere, particularly the windfields and temperature/humidity profile that are vital for defining cloud formation, water, energy and aerosol transport.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

<https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/reanalysis-era5-single-levels?tab=overview>

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

No

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Copernicus

<https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/reanalysis-era5-single-levels?tab=form>

Copernicus is the Earth observation component of the European Union's Space programme, looking at our planet and its environment to benefit all European citizens. It offers information services that draw from satellite Earth Observation and in-situ (non-space) data.

The European Commission manages the Programme. It is implemented in partnership with the Member States, the European Space Agency (ESA), the European Organisation for the Exploitation of Meteorological Satellites (EUMETSAT), the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF), EU Agencies and Mercator Océan.

Vast amounts of global data from satellites and ground-based, airborne, and seaborne measurement systems provide information to help service providers, public authorities, and other international organisations improve European citizens' quality of life and beyond. The information services provided are free and openly accessible to users.

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

- Has certification
- Follows repository standards
- Details terms of use
- Has an open access content policy
- Provides Open Access content (free at the point of use)
- Assigns PIDs
- Uses non-proprietary formats
- Supports mid- and long-term preservation
- Supports authentication and authorization of users
- Has data security mechanisms in place

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

Storage

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

MODIS gridded cloud and aerosol data (MOD08_D3)

Collection 6.1

Gridded cloud and aerosol data from the MODIS instrument. This data is derived from the pixel level (L2) retrievals produced by the MODIS atmosphere science team, incorporating retrievals of cloud, aerosol, water vapour and the atmospheric profile.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

Re-used

MODIS data used to analyse and constrain aerosol-cloud interactions

<https://ladsweb.modaps.eosdis.nasa.gov/missions-and-measurements/science-domain/l3-atmosphere/>.

Additional information about the sources and construction of the L3 data product are given in the ATDB

https://atmosphere-imager.gsfc.nasa.gov/sites/default/files/ModAtmo/documents/L3_ATBD_C6_C61_2020_08_06.pdf

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Derived or compiled

The Level-3 MODIS Atmosphere Daily Global Product contains roughly 600 statistical datasets that are derived from approximately 80 scientific parameters from four Level-2 MODIS Atmosphere Products: Aerosol (04_L2), Water Vapor (05_L2), Cloud (06_L2), and Atmosphere Profile (07_L2).

This entry describes collection 6.1 of the dataset.

1.1.5 What is its format?

hdf

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

1000000000000

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To develop a product

These data from the MODIS instrument provide an un-matched long-term, quality assured, global retrieved product describing aerosol and cloud properties.

In combination with the other datasets used as part of this project, the MODIS product allows the characterisation of aerosol and cloud temporal development over a range of timescales.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

<https://atmosphere-imager.gsfc.nasa.gov/products/daily>

The MODIS products are produced from the instrument measured radiances. The retrievals use these data, along with ancillary products (such as land cover, aerosol-type distributions), to retrieve the provided geophysical properties.

The algorithms are described in

doi: 10.1109/TGRS.2016.2610522 (cloud product)

doi: 10.1002/2014JD022453 (aerosol product)

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

10.5067/MODIS/MOD08_D3.061 (Terra)

10.5067/MODIS/MYD08_D3.061 (Aqua)

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

No

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

NASA Data Portal

<https://ladsweb.modaps.eosdis.nasa.gov>

Download site for MODIS data (radiances and retrieved products). LAADS DAAC primarily archives and distributes data on clouds, water vapor, and aerosols in Earth's atmosphere as well as key instrument data for NASA, NOAA and European Space Administration missions. LAADS DAAC also serves as a backup source for MODIS and VIIRS land products.

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

- Has certification
- Follows repository standards
- Details terms of use
- Has an open access content policy

- Provides Open Access content (free at the point of use)
- Assigns PIDs
- Uses non-proprietary formats
- Supports mid- and long-term preservation
- Supports authentication and authorization of users
- Has data security mechanisms in place

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

Already public and supported by NASA

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

Storage

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

GOES ABI radiances

Radiances from the GOES ABI instrument. These cover a range of visible and infrared wavelengths, providing information on cloud, aerosol and land surface properties. The spatial resolution depends on wavelength, varying from 500m to 2km at nadir.

This data is re-used from publicly available data (via NASA and Google/Amazon clouds)

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

Re-used

Radiances from the GOES ABI instrument will be used as part of the analysis. The GOES ABI instruments provide high spatial and temporal resolution data

across much of the Atlantic and Pacific oceans, including large areas of stratocumulus cloud known to be important for aerosol-cloud interactions.

The Advanced Baseline Imager (ABI) operates on board the NOAA Geostationary Operational Environmental Satellite-R (GOES-R) Series weather satellites providing advanced imagery and atmospheric measurements of Earth's Western Hemisphere. The Advanced Baseline Imager (ABI) instrument samples the radiance of the Earth in sixteen spectral bands using several arrays of detectors in the instrument's focal plane. Single reflective band ABI Level 1b Radiance Products (channels 1 - 6 with approximate center wavelengths 0.47, 0.64, 0.865, 1.378, 1.61, 2.25 microns, respectively) are digital maps of outgoing radiance values at the top of the atmosphere for visible and near-infrared (IR) bands. Single emissive band ABI L1b Radiance Products (channels 7 - 16 with approximate center wavelengths 3.9, 6.185, 6.95, 7.34, 8.5, 9.61, 10.35, 11.2, 12.3, 13.3 microns, respectively) are digital maps of outgoing radiance values at the top of the atmosphere for IR bands. Detector samples are compressed, packetized and down-linked to the ground station as Level 0 data for conversion to calibrated, geo-located pixels (Level 1b Radiance data). The detector samples are decompressed, radiometrically corrected, navigated and resampled onto an invariant output grid, referred to as the ABI fixed grid. There are three spatial coverage scenes per satellite (GOES East and GOES West): Full Disk is the full hemispheric view; Contiguous U.S. is the lower 48 states; and Mesoscale 1 and 2 are for weather event views.

More information is available at

<https://www.avl.class.noaa.gov/saa/products/welcome>

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Observational

The Advanced Baseline Imager is the primary instrument on the GOES-R Series for imaging Earth's weather, oceans and environment. ABI views the Earth with 16 different spectral bands (compared to five on the previous generation of GOES), including two visible channels, four near-infrared channels, and ten infrared channels. These different channels (wavelengths) are used by models and tools to indicate various elements on the Earth's surface or in the atmosphere, such as trees, water, clouds, moisture or smoke.

1.1.5 What is its format?

netcdf

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

1000000000000

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To develop a product

These data provide the highest spatial and temporal resolution data currently available from geostationary satellites (until new Meteosat data becomes available)

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

<https://www.avl.class.noaa.gov/saa/products/welcome>

Produced by NOAA< the data is either downloaded directly from NOAA or the Google/Amazon clouds, where it is also stored.

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

No

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

NOAA Comprehensive Large Array-Data Stewardship System

<https://www.avl.class.noaa.gov/saa/products/welcome>

The Comprehensive Large Array-data Stewardship System (CLASS) is an electronic library of NOAA environmental data. This web site provides capabilities for finding and obtaining those data.

CLASS is NOAA's premiere on-line facility for the distribution of NOAA and US Department of Defense (DoD) Polar-orbiting Operational Environmental Satellite (POES) data, NOAA's Geostationary Operational Environmental Satellite (GOES) data, and derived data.

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

- Has certification
- Follows repository standards
- Details terms of use
- Has an open access content policy
- Provides Open Access content (free at the point of use)
- Assigns PIDs
- Uses non-proprietary formats
- Supports mid- and long-term preservation
- Supports authentication and authorization of users
- Has data security mechanisms in place

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

Re-use

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

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